

CAUSES AND PREVENTION OF TUBERCULOSIS AMONG STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION COUNTRIES

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Annotation. In 2017-2022, the state of respiratory tuberculosis was analyzed in 71 students of higher educational institutions located in Surkhandarya region. It has been shown that primary infection with tuberculosis mycobacteria in higher educational institutions can be considered as a risk factor for the subsequent development of the disease. The need for special prevention (BCG revaccination) for students of higher educational institutions, especially in the period of epidemiological problems.

Key words: tuberculosis, seasonality of the disease, students of higher education institutions, susceptibility, prevention.

Relevance of the study. The epidemiological situation of tuberculosis remains acute in most regions of Uzbekistan, including Surkhandarya region. The problem of tuberculosis is of particular importance among medical workers, who, by the nature of their professional activity, are not only one of the most vulnerable groups in terms of the onset of the disease, but also pose an epidemiological risk for their patients [1]. It fully applies to students of higher education institutions, who are considered an independent risk group of tuberculosis [2], therefore, the issues of identifying and preventing tuberculosis among this population group are an urgent problem.

In the tuberculosis dispensary, scientific work on the timely detection of tuberculosis among students is constantly conducted. Currently, every spring, a screening fluorographic examination (PFLGO) was conducted by a mobile fluorograph provided by the Tuberculosis Dispensary located in the city of Termiz.

The purpose of the study. During 2017-2022, to conduct analyzes of tuberculosis in the respiratory organs of students of higher educational institutions and to justify the need for specific prevention of tuberculosis among students of Surkhandarya region.

Research materials and methods. 71 students of higher educational institutions with newly diagnosed respiratory tuberculosis participated in the research. The methods of disease detection, the time elapsed since the previous fluoroscopy, the structure and characteristics of the clinical forms of the tuberculosis process, the nature of the accompanying pathology, the treatment used and its effectiveness were analyzed.

Discussion of research results. The results of the study showed that among the patients - men - 41.3%, women - 58.7%. Consequently, their ratio was 1:1.4, which is significantly different from the regional average of 2:1. The majority of patients (76.1%) are 21-30 years old, 19.6% are under 20 years old, and only 4.3% are 31-40 years old.

Students were divided according to the form of education as follows: 37 (52%) patients were in full-time education, 18 (25.6%) were in part-time education, 12 (17%) were in second higher education, evening education in the form of lime - 4 (5.6%). Tuberculosis developed in only 17.4% in I-II courses; III-IV - 52.2%. It appears that the disease developed

when the students began working directly with patients in the clinics, proving that exposure to Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MBT) and the development of the disease in the future are possible. The seasonality of the disease attracts attention: the largest number of patients was recorded in spring (80.4%); much less - in winter (10.9%) and in autumn - (8.7%).

In 10.9% of the patients, it was found that there was contact at the workplace.

All of them have secondary specialized medical education, and their studies are combined with work. 52.2% lived in families, the rest (47.8%) lived in dormitories.

More than half of the patients (56.5%) were diagnosed during a visit to the doctor, with PFLHO - 43.5%. Analysis of the time of fluoroscopic examination before the diagnosis of the disease showed that in 6.5% of cases it was up to 6 months, in 34.8% - up to 1 year, in 39.1% - up to 2 years, and in 19.6% - 2 or more years .

Thus, in 58.7% of cases, its deadlines were violated, which requires stricter control of students' passing of fluorofluorescence exams by the deans.

The analysis of the characteristics of the tuberculosis process in the lungs, which occurred in 43 patients, showed that 60.5% had limited (1-2 segment) processes, 39.5% had widespread (proportional or more) processes. Pulmonary tissue destruction was detected in 50.0% of cases, bacterial excretion in 54.6% of cases.

Biomedical risk factors for the development of tuberculosis (chronic non-specific lung diseases, diabetes, stomach and duodenal ulcers) were identified in every third patient.

All patients underwent etiotropic chemotherapy, taking into account the sensitivity of MBT to antibacterial drugs, pathogenetic therapy and, if necessary, surgical treatment. Operations were performed in 17.4% of cases: bisegmental resection - 10.9% (together with thoracoplasty in one case), lobectomy - 2.2%, diagnostic thoracotomy with pleural biopsy - 4.3%. No complications were observed in the postoperative period. 10.9% of patients were treated in sanatorium-spa.

Summary. During the study period, some of the students get sick with tuberculosis before graduation. Tuberculosis is a high-risk infection that can become a disease under certain conditions. In this regard, taking into account the acute epidemiological situation and the highest rate of tuberculosis in young students, we consider it appropriate to revaccinate uninfected students as a high-risk group.

References:

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